

Short Communication

A small terrestrial mammal survey and analysis of bait consumption at Bokor National Park, Cambodia

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Cambodia boasts a rich array of species and the Greater Cardamom Mountains in the country's South-west are recognised as part of a global biodiversity hotspot (Myers *et al.*, 2000) and one of the planet's 200 Global Ecoregions (Olson *et al.*, 2000). Survey effort in this region has recently intensified and uncovered new species of plants (Mey, 2009), amphibians and reptiles (e.g. Daltry & Wuster, 2002; Grismer *et al.*, 2008; Neang *et al.*, 2012). Medium-sized to large mammals have also been a research focus in Cambodia, with several papers describing their distribution, populations and threats (e.g. Emmett & Olssen, 2005; Royan, 2010; Edwards *et al.*, 2012; Gray *et al.*, 2012). In contrast, little work has been conducted on the small terrestrial mammals of Cambodia. Bats (order Chiroptera) have been the most intensively researched small mammals in Cambodia, with 70 species presently known (Chheang *et al.*, 2013), including taxa new to science (Csorba, 2011; Csorba *et al.*, 2011). However, a recent study identified a new species of shrew (Jenkins *et al.*, 2010).

Within the Cardamom Mountains, only two systematic surveys of small terrestrial mammals have been reported. The first used aluminium box traps and pitfall traps and caught mostly rodents (Muridae) except for a single capture of the insectivore *Hylomys suillus* (Swan & Kry, 2000). The second study employed box, pitfall and mesh traps and encountered two

species of shrew (*Crocidura* spp.), two species of tree shrews and eight rats (Emmett & Olssen, 2005).

Capture rates for small terrestrial mammals in forested ecosystems in Cambodia tend to be low. For instance, Swan & Kry (2000) recorded a mean capture rate of 1.3% and 0.9% for small terrestrial mammals in the Phnom Samkos Wildlife Sanctuary, while Emmett & Olssen (2005) achieved a capture rate of 2.6% for small and medium-sized mammals using traps in the Central Cardamoms Protected Forest. These are similar to the capture rates of 0.04–2.6% in northern Cambodia (Edwards *et al.*, 2012), but lower than a study of rodents across four habitat types in eastern and southern Cambodia, including settlements and agricultural areas (mean 13.5%: Ivanova *et al.*, 2012).

The type of bait used to attract mammals can significantly affect the species and number of individuals trapped (Patric, 1970; Kok *et al.*, 2013). Most studies in Cambodia have used vegetable matter, including sticky rice, peanuts, bananas and/or cassava as bait (Kemper & Bell, 1985; Swan & Kry, 2000; Emmett & Olssen, 2005; Blasdell *et al.*, 2011; Edwards *et al.*, 2012; Starr *et al.*, 2012), but two studies used dried fish or shrimp (Swan & Kry, 2000; Conservation International, 2007), one used dried beef (Conservation International, 2007) and one used chicken or egg (Starr *et al.*, 2012). Shrews may be particularly attracted to meat lures, but little is known of these

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Fig. 1 Location of study sites in Bokor National Park, Cambodia. Site 1 was at $10^{\circ}43.826'N$, $103^{\circ}55.601'E$, at an elevation of 408 metres above sea level (asl), and consisted of wet dipterocarp forest with bananas and sugar palms. Canopy cover was estimated at $>80\%$ and there was extensive ground cover with many fallen logs. Site 2 was at $10^{\circ}45.542'N$, $103^{\circ}55.154'E$, at an elevation of 416 m asl, and consisted of drier dipterocarp forest with none of large-leaved plants that occurred in Site 1. Canopy cover was estimated at $>60\%$ and there was less ground cover than in Site 1.

species in Cambodia (Emmett & Olssen, 2005; Jenkins *et al.*, 2010). As species composition is likely to vary markedly across Cambodia and different bait types may affect the numbers of species attracted to traps, this paper reports the results of a pilot investigation of small mammal assemblages and their bait consumption in two sites in Bokor National Park.

Bokor National Park (Fig. 1) covers an area of $>1,400$ km² and is in the Elephant Mountains of Cambodia (Seng *et al.*, 2003), a southern offshoot of the Cardamom Mountains. The small mammal study was undertaken at two sites in the southern portion of the park from 11–24 February 2013 as part of a broader biodiversity study investigating amphibians, reptiles, birds, bats, large mammals and gibbons from October 2012 to May 2013.

In Site 1 (Fig. 1), Elliott small live mammal traps (9 cm \times 10 cm \times 33 cm) were set along a transect at approximately 15–20 m intervals for a total of 60

trap-nights. In Site 2 (Fig. 1), Elliott traps were set for a total of 50 trap-nights along four transects with approximately 15–20 m intervals between traps. The four transects were along a dry creek bed (15 trap-nights), off a steep path (21 trap-nights), on a sloped path (six trap-nights) and along a stream (eight trap-nights). Where necessary, traps were moved within their chosen locations to protect trapped animals from ants and to reduce the amount of bait consumed by non-target species.

Traps were placed in areas likely to be used by mammals including alongside fallen logs, under boulders, and near runways, holes and observed scats. All traps were checked at dawn (≈ 0630 h), midday (≈ 1300 h) and dusk (≈ 1730 h). Every trap was covered with thick plastic to protect animals from wind and rain and was filled with cotton wadding and tissue paper to provide nesting material. As animal preferences for bait were unknown, every trap was baited simultaneously with ≈ 5 g of locally produced

lap cheong (fatty pork salami), uncooked rice, dried papaya, dried cranberries, liver dog treats and a mixed ball of peanut butter, rolled oats and honey. Following every capture, the remaining bait was collected and the amount consumed was assigned to the following classes: 100%, 75–99%, 50–74%, 25–49% and <25%.

Upon capture, every animal was weighed using a Pesola™ 60 g or 600 g spring balance and measured using vernier callipers. Reproductive status and age class were also recorded (Aplin *et al.*, 2003). On their first capture, animals were individually marked with a unique set of ear clips and the removed tissue was stored in 90% ethanol for genetic analyses. Animals were generally handled in cloth bags, but the *Maxomys* sp. was measured briefly in a large clear plastic bag because the animals appeared calmer and handling of their delicate tail skin was avoided (Francis, 2008). Genetic samples were deposited and stored at -20°C at the Royal University of Phnom Penh Centre for Biodiversity Conservation (they will be analysed at the Museum Victoria, Australia). Following measurement, all animals were released at their point of capture.

All captures occurred overnight with no animals trapped during daylight hours. There were 29 successful captures from 110 trap-nights giving an overall capture rate of 26%.

From the total of 60 trap-nights in Site 1, four specimens were trapped, giving a capture rate of 7%. They included a 160 g female rat with silver upperparts, white underparts and feet, and a mottled grey tail (Fig. 2), which was identified as *Berylmys berdmorei*, albeit smaller than published measurements for this species (Aplin *et al.*, 2003). Two female shrews were trapped, which were dark grey with a tail shorter than their head-body length and had sparse hairs near the base of the tail (Fig. 3). They weighed 7.3 and 7.5 g (mean 7.4 g) and had a distinctive musky odour. These animals were likely in the genus *Crocidura*, but their measurements did not match any species presently known in Cambodia or Southeast Asia. A palm civet *Paradoxurus hermaphrodites* was also trapped, but after consuming the bait it broke out of the trap and was subsequently identified from its hair and scats.

A total of 50 trap-nights were conducted in Site 2 with 15 rats (seven females, eight males) trapped on 25 occasions (including 10 recaptures), giving a capture rate of 50%. The rats' upperparts were a distinctive reddish-orange colour with a darker midline and numerous stiff dark spines throughout the fur (Fig. 4). Underparts were white with small stiff spines and

Fig. 2 Rat resembling *Berylmys berdmorei* trapped in Site 1.

Fig. 3 *Crocidura* sp. trapped in Site 1.

Fig. 4 *Maxomys* sp. trapped in Site 2 (being briefly held in plastic bag).

were sharply demarcated from upperparts. The tail was bicoloured, being dark grey above and white underneath, with a white tip comprising one-third of the tail length. Feet were white and ears were dark grey. Mean mass was 170.27 ± 22.38 g (males 173.6 ± 21.6 g; females 166.4 ± 24.3 g) and ranged from 130–209 g. This species appeared most similar to *Maxomys surifer* (Aplin *et al.*, 2003), but had a number of differences, including consistently shorter ears. The rats were all adults in breeding condition with enlarged testes in the males and signs of early-mid pregnancy in three of the seven females.

Rates of bait consumption by the rodents were: lap *cheong* 100%, dog treats 50–74%, bait ball 50–74%, dried papaya 25–49%, dried cranberries 25–49% and rice <25%. The shrews consumed lap *cheong* only. The *Maxomys* rats trapped on consecutive nights gained between 2–13 g (mean 5.14 ± 1.64 g), the equivalent of up to 8% of their body mass, indicating that large amounts of bait had been consumed.

This is the first study of small terrestrial mammals at Bokor National Park, and insectivores, carnivores and rodents were trapped. To the best of our knowledge, the trap success rate achieved at Site 2 (50%) is the highest recorded for small terrestrial mammals in Cambodia to date. This may be attributed to the rats occurring at high population densities, becoming “trap happy” (whereby individuals that are trapped have a positive experience and are more inclined to enter traps again), and/or the use of more attractive baits.

The pork-based lap *cheong* was entirely consumed by all species caught, and shrews consumed this bait alone. This is likely due to their small size (≈ 7.4 g) and inability to eat any further items during their brief period in the traps. Rodents also consumed greater amounts of liver dog treats and bait ball mixture than dried fruits. Little to no rice was consumed. This mirrors studies in South Africa where peanut butter and oat mixes were the most successful bait, achieving more captures than fruit or meat lures (Kok *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, peanut butter mixes are the most effective lure in the USA, although meat lures are effective at attracting carnivores (Patric, 1970). However, a study of arboreal species in Cambodia found banana to be a more effective lure than chicken for small and medium-sized mammals, including carnivores (Starr *et al.*, 2012). Small mammal surveys in Cambodia have commonly used fruit or sticky rice as bait (Kemper & Bell, 1985; Swan & Kry, 2000; Blasdell *et al.*, 2011), although two studies also used dried fish, shrimp and beef (Swan & Kry, 2000; Conservation International,

2007). We recommend the use of multiple food types, including meat lures and peanut butter mixes, to increase capture success in Cambodia.

This short study may have uncovered new species of rat and shrew, but further genetic and morphological work is required and will be conducted shortly. Further studies on shrews are likely to uncover new records for Cambodia and potentially species new to science. In 2004, Emmett & Olssen (2005) collected two unidentified species of shrew. Two further unidentified species were found in Virachey National Park in 2007 (Conservation International, 2007), and a new species of *Crocidura* was recently described from Northeast Cambodia (Jenkins *et al.*, 2010). Among the rodents, the genus *Maxomys* in particular has highly divergent populations within and between island regions (Achmadi *et al.*, 2013) and new *Maxomys* species continue to be described (e.g. Achmadi *et al.*, 2012). Emmett & Olssen (2005) also discovered *Maxomys* and *Niviventer* species in the Cardamom Mountains which appear to differ externally from previously recorded species. With so little research on small terrestrial mammals in Cambodia, new records and possibly new species likely await discovery.

Further research and allied conservation initiatives are vital to protect biodiversity in Bokor National Park. Several areas within the park are likely to support high numbers of small mammal species and need protection from inappropriate land-use. More intensive small mammal surveys, using a variety of traps and baits over a longer time period in different regions of Bokor National Park, and Cambodia as a whole, are required to elucidate species diversity and conservation requirements for future management.

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